

THE HISTORY OF THE ORIGIN OF ACTION GAMES. IMPORTANCE OF NATIONAL FOLK GAMES IN EDUCATION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract

This article contains various comments about the history of games. The importance of games, action games, and national games in the life and education of preschool children was discussed.

Key words: game, action games, national folk games, education, types of games, social event, history, features of games

INTRODUCTION

"The future begins today," said Islam Karimov, the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in his speech at the extraordinary ninth session of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan of the 12th convocation. "If we don't pay attention to the issue of education now, the future will be wasted."

Spiritual and moral purification, faith, honesty, piety, honor, kindness, and other truly human qualities do not come by themselves. Education is the basis of everything.

According to historical data, hunting games played an important role in the lives of primitive hunters. In some sources, it is written that they are held before the hunt, while in others, opinions are expressed about the games held after the hunt.

If these data are analyzed in depth, it can be said that hunting games were held both before and after hunting. Pre-hunting games - at first, served as an exercise (checking readiness for hunting, mental and physical preparation for hunting), and serious small primitive people learned how to easily capture and approach the prey. For this, they put on a mask and practiced impersonating an animal, its behavior and sounds. It was during these games that young people were taught to hunt. Therefore, it served as a kind of school, on the one hand, it helped to develop the skills of hunters, and on the other hand, it formed and developed the art of imitation in them.

In the early periods, noisy chaotic games were increasingly performed through pantomime of musical tones and plastic movements. In the later periods, games of such ethnographic interpretation moved into various forms, such as "Bear game", "Giant game", "Monkey game", then "Dog game", "Horse game", "Humron stake game", "Goat game", "Wolf game", "Eagle Game", "Rabbit Game", "Fox Game", "Jack-Jaku Game" etc. It is known that plays, pantomimes are passed down from generation to generation. They are directly or indirectly related to children's folklore games. In this way, the word "game" is related to the word "play" of the Turkic peoples (it means house, mind, wisdom). Expressing mind and understanding through movement and gestures is important in the birth of games.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

Uzbek traditional children's folklore games have a wide range of topics and performance styles. There is no aspect of social life, human relations, which has not come under the eyes of games. Our people's views on agriculture, animal husbandry, horticulture, policing, culture, professions and science, philosophical, aesthetic, moral, education, ethics - all traditional games is the subject. In particular, Uzbek children's folklore games are full of spiritual, educational and moral concepts. In the historical path of our people, which has passed through thousands of years, after repeatedly passing through experiments and tests, becoming whole and perfect, children's folklore games that have reached us can be divided into the following types depending on the direction of the content:

1. Seasonal children's folklore games (folklore games played in early spring, summer, winter seasons).
2. Ceremonial children's folklore games (rituals, customs, rituals, games played during traditional holidays).
3. Family-household children's folklore games ("Guest-guest", "Bride drop-off", "Bride-groom", "Mother and child", "Cooking", "House furnishing", "Doll game", "Creating bread", "Couple", "Alla-Alla", "Decorating a crib" and others).
4. Children's folklore games with physical movement ("Goose-geese", "Chasing the ball", "White bone", "Ball-stone", "Break", "White poplar-blue poplar", "Horse game", "The girl chased" and others).
5. Logical children's folklore games (quick sayings, riddles, counting games, sayings, questions and answers, inventions, memory recovery, guesswork, etc.).
6. Children's folklore games related to animals and natural phenomena.
7. Fun children's folklore games.
8. Music games.

Folk games, including children's folklore games, from the earliest times, embodying the people's way of life, spiritual-educational, physical fitness, aesthetic worldview, have grown to this day and deepened according to the purpose of the content. Unlike other forms of art, games clearly reflect the people's spirit, psychology, color, attitude to the education of the young generation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A game is a historically formed social event, an independent type of activity, unique to a person. Play activities are very diverse: children's games with toys, board games, circle games, movement games, sports games. The game can be a means of self-knowledge, entertainment, recreation, a means of physical and general social education, a means of sports. As an element of game culture, it develops society with all its culture and various needs of people: it occupies a great place in entertainment, recreation, development of spiritual, mental and physical strength.

Game activity is not only an element of culture, but also a useful tool for educating children and adolescents. It is always goal-oriented and characterized by a variety of purposeful guidance and purposeful action. Play activities have more in common with work, especially during childhood. However, a person cannot create material wealth to satisfy life needs during the game.

Play is a very fun and energetic activity, so it is a great asset in educational work with young people and children. The most common type of game among young and old, especially among teenagers and children, are action games.

A distinctive feature of action games is the vivid expression of the role of movement in the content of the game (running, jumping, throwing, shooting, passing and catching the ball, resisting, etc.). This moving movement gives it its content (theme, idea). He is directed to overcome various difficulties and obstacles on the way to achieve the goal set in the game.

Action games are distinguished between (elementary) action games and sports games. In fact, (elementary) action games embody the voluntary initiative of the players, which are voluntarily set, conditionally directed to the achievement of the goal.

Achieving the goal requires an active movement of the players, the performance of which depends on the creativity and initiative of the players (quickly running to the target, quickly shooting at the target, quickly and dexterously reaching or escaping from the "Opponent" and etc.).

A lot of historical information about the description and appearance of these games can be found in the scientific works of our great ancestors. We can find a lot of interesting and useful information about Uzbek national games in the book "Devon-u lug`oti turk" by Mahmud Koshgari, "Canon of Medicine" by Abu Ali ibn Sina, and "Kabusnoma" by Kaikovus. Umar Khayyom "Navro'znoma", Yusuf Khos Khajib "Qutad-g`u bilig", Husain Vaiz Koshifiy "Fituvvatnomayi Sultoniy yohud Javonmardlik tarigati ", Alisher Navoi "Khamsa", Pirmkul Kadirov "Starry Nights", Mirmuhsin "Temur Malik". Such historical, scientific and artistic works, the history of the emergence of folk games are presented in interesting facts. and get acquainted with the history of the game, but also with historical, scientific and literary literature they get acquainted with the works of our ancestors. The influence of games on physical development and their pedagogical features in raising a healthy and intelligent generation can be considered on the example of several national outdoor games.

CONCLUSION

The purpose of the national open games of the Uzbek people is to raise the young generation to be strong and brave ancestors, this can be achieved by mastering the outdoor games of the people, in addition to this, national games can be developed and awakened in children and young people. Interest and respect for the history, culture, and traditions of the Uzbek national games. Sport is a decisive force in creating a healthy environment, raising a well-rounded generation, and developing moral excellence. We are still developing; we still have to solve important educational problems. If we pay attention to the emergence and formation of mobile national Uzbek games, then its roots go back to the distant past, a long history. The main manifestations of national physical culture are personal games, fights, legends, heroic epics, its expressions are created in dance and music. The material and spiritual heritage left by our ancestors is evidence of the history of the emergence of folk games. The history of the emergence of folk games is the first stage in the development of historical-archaeological society and the emergence of folk games in ethnographic sources, and we also find interesting information about the development of national Uzbek outdoor sports games.

Game activity is not only an element of culture, but also a useful tool for educating children and adolescents.

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